

Flexible RAN: a Radio Access Network Concept with Flexible Functional Splits and a Programmable Optical Transport

Yajie Li^(1,2), Jonas Mårtensson⁽³⁾, Matteo Fiorani⁽⁴⁾, Björn Skubic⁽⁴⁾, Zere Ghebretensaé⁽⁴⁾, Yongli Zhao⁽²⁾, Jie Zhang⁽²⁾, Lena Wosinska⁽¹⁾, Paolo Monti⁽¹⁾

⁽¹⁾ KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Kista, Sweden

⁽²⁾ Beijing University of Posts and Telecommunication, Beijing, China (yajieli@bupt.edu.cn)

⁽³⁾ RISE Acreo, Kista, Sweden, ⁽⁴⁾ Ericsson, Kista, Sweden

Abstract We present the flexible RAN concept and evaluate its performance in different radio coordination scenarios considering an optical transport network. Results show the benefits of flexible RAN compared to C-RAN in terms of wavelength usage and transponder cost.

Introduction

Recently, 3GPP¹ discussed different potential baseband processing functions (BPFs) splits between the central unit (CU) and the radio units (RUs) in Cloud Radio Access Network (C-RAN) architecture. A low layer split, e.g., low-physical (PHY), can support advanced radio coordination techniques, e.g., Joint Reception (JR) Coordinated MultiPoint (JR-CoMP). However, the interface between low-PHY and the rest of the BPF chain (i.e., referred to as enhanced Common Public Radio Interface – eCPRI²) requires a high-capacity transport. With a high layer split, e.g., between the Packet Data Convergence Protocol (PDCP) and the Radio Link Control layer (RLC), the transport capacity required on the interface between RLC and PDCP (referred to as F1³) is lower than for eCPRI. However, this split makes it difficult to implement advanced radio coordination functions. The choice of BPF split and consequently the transport capacity requirements are determined by the RUs' radio coordination needs⁴. Another aspect to consider is the physical location of the BPFs. The closer the BPFs are to the RUs, the lower is the number of eCPRI flows to be accommodated by the transport network. On the other hand, tight radio coordination schemes require joint processing of eCPRI flows from all the RUs involved (i.e., high level of BPFs aggregation). A C-RAN architecture is not able to capture this trade-off. All the BPFs reside in the CU (regardless of the actual radio coordination needs), resulting in high transport resource requirements, regardless of the actual radio network needs. The authors in⁵ tried to address this problem by designing an adaptive placement of BPFs in different traffic conditions. However, they considered only MAC/PHY split option and did not consider the role of radio coordination.

This paper proposes a new RAN concept referred to as *Flexible RAN (F-RAN)*. In an F-

RAN, BPFs are strategically distributed within the RAN in order to optimize the trade-off between radio performance maximization and transport capacity requirement minimization. The results presented in the paper quantify the reduced requirements on fiber resources for F-RAN compared to C-RAN for both ring and tree topologies, and under different radio interference management scenarios.

F-RAN Concept and Use Case Definition

In this work, the F-RAN concept is applied to a radio network using a Dense Wavelength Division Multiplexing (DWDM) centric transport⁶. RUs are connected to Metro Nodes (MNs) via Access Edge (AE) nodes. In turn, MNs can reach the 5G Core via a Metro Edge (ME) node (Fig. 1). In an F-RAN, low-PHY functionalities are placed at the RUs while PDCP functions are placed at the ME. The other BPFs can be placed either at the MNs, a concept referred to as *Fully Distributed F-RAN (FDF-RAN)*, or at both MNs and MEs, i.e., a concept referred to as *Partially Centralized F-RAN (PCF-RAN)*. Flexibility in the transport is introduced by means of both packet and wavelength (i.e., λ) aggregation functionalities available at MNs. The former is used for the F1 traffic, the latter for the eCPRI traffic.

Fig. 1: Flexible RAN concept

The F-RAN concept has been applied to a use case where radio coordination functions are used to manage radio interference. Under the assumption that RUs connected to the same MN belong to the same coordination area (CA), we

Fig. 2: Coordination scenarios in PCF-RAN and FDF-RAN

consider two types of interference: (i) *intra-CA* (i.e., among RUs belonging to the same CA), and (ii) *inter-CA interference* (i.e., among RUs belonging to different CAs). For interference management, we assume tight radio coordination schemes (i.e., eCPRI flows from RUs that require coordination must be terminated at the same BPFs to meet the coordination constraints).

Fig. 2 shows how the PCF-RAN and FDF-RAN concepts can be applied in different interference management scenarios while considering different optical transport topologies. The nodes colored in yellow are the ones equipped with BPFs. Fig. 2(a) and (b) refer to the PCF-RAN case with an optical ring and tree transport topology. To manage intra-CA interference, eCPRI flows from RUs in the same CA are terminated at the local MN. After baseband processing, the resulting F1 traffic is aggregated to reduce the wavelength usage in metro links. To manage inter-CA interference, eCPRI flows are optically switched at the MN and terminated at the ME. Fig. 2(c) and 2(d) refer to the FDF-RAN case. For the intra-CA case, the interference is managed as it was done in the PCF-RAN case. However, for inter-CA interference, the system first selects a *master BPF node* where all the eCPRI flows need to be terminated. This is to enforce tight coordination among the RUs requiring interference management. For example, in Fig.2(c), the traffic from RU_C optically bypasses MN₂ and terminates in MN₁. After baseband processing, two F1 traffic flows are aggregated from MN₁ to ME. In Fig. 2(d), MN₁ is also selected as the master BPF node with the only difference that the eCPRI flow from RU_C to MN₁ is optically switched at MN₂ and at ME. The next section evaluates the benefits of using an F-RAN architecture in terms of optical

transport resource usage, with the envisioned radio interference management cases.

Simulation setup, results and analysis

To evaluate the benefits of F-RAN, we consider an optical transport with both a ring and a tree topology, each one with three MNs and one ME. We assume that each MN is connected to fifteen AEs which, in turn, have six RUs each, for a total of 270 RUs. For the ring topology, routing and wavelength assignment is done according to the strategy presented in⁶, while for the tree topology we use a minimum hop for the routing and a first fit for the wavelength assignment. The ratio between eCPRI and F1 capacity is assumed to be 1:10. As a result, each wavelength can support one eCPRI traffic flow or ten F1 traffic flows⁷. We assume that each fiber supports 80 wavelength channels. Simulation results are obtained by averaging a total of 200 experiments. In each experiment, the number of RUs that require interference management is randomly generated and uniformly distributed among the RUs connected to each AE. It is also assumed that when a RU requires interference management, it will be of the inter-CA type. When considering FDF-RAN, inter-CA interference management can involve two or three CAs at the same time. We consider three scenarios: (i) inter-CA between 2 CAs (2CA), (ii) inter-CA among 3 CAs (3CA), and (iii) 50% of RUs requiring interference management with a 2CA profile and 50% with a 3CA profile (50%-2CA-50%-3CA). In FDF-RAN, the master BPF node is selected as the one connected to the highest number of RUs that require interference management. The performance analysis of F-RAN focuses on two parameters: (i) the number of wavelengths on the most loaded link in the ring/tree portion of the transport connecting the MNs to the ME, and (ii)

the total number of transponders (TPs) required in each in transport network. The performance of F-RAN is benchmarked with C-RAN.

Figure 3 shows the wavelength usage for F-RAN with a ring topology as a function of the percentage of RUs requiring radio interference management. In C-RAN, the wavelength requirements are independent of radio coordination needs. In PCF-RAN and FDF-RAN, the number of wavelengths increases with the number of RUs that need inter-CA interference management. For the same RU number, FDF-RAN requires fewer wavelengths than PCF-RAN. In addition, in the FDF-RAN case, different interference management profiles have a different impact on the wavelength usage in the transport network, i.e., the higher the number of CAs involved, the higher the number of wavelengths required in the metro ring. Fig. 4 shows the number of extra TP pairs needed in F-RAN compared to the 270 TP pairs required by C-RAN. In PCF-RAN, the number of extra TP pairs decreases with the number of RUs requiring interference management, i.e., more RU coordination leads to less F1 flow aggregation. In FDF-RAN, the number of extra TP pairs is constant at around 11%, i.e., the number of extra TPs needed to aggregate the F1 traffic.

Fig. 3: Number of wavelengths in most loaded metro link

Fig. 4: Number of extra TP pairs in the network

Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 show the amount of transport resources needed for F-RAN in a tree based optical transport network. As opposed to the ring topology case, PCF-RAN shows similar or better

performance in terms of the number of required wavelengths when compared to FDF-RAN (Fig. 5). In some cases (i.e., 50%-2CA-50%-3CA) with a high number of RUs requiring interference management, the number of wavelengths needed by FDF-RAN is even higher than for C-RAN. On the other hand, in terms of the number of extra TP pairs, the behavior is similar to the ring topology case.

Fig. 5: Number of wavelengths in most loaded metro link

Fig. 6: Number of extra TP pairs in the network

Conclusions

This paper proposes two variants for F-RAN, i.e., PCF-RAN and FDF-RAN. The performance of PCF-RAN and FDF-RAN is evaluated in scenarios with different radio needs and assuming an optical transport network with both ring and tree topology. Results confirm that overall F-RAN achieves a better efficiency in utilization of transport resources compared to conventional C-RAN.

Acknowledgements

This work has the support of the Kista 5G Transport Lab (K5) project funded by VINNOVA and Ericsson and of the H2020-ICT-2014 project 5GEx (Grant Agreement no. 671636).

References

- [1] 3GPP TSG RAN WG3, TR 38.801, February 2017.
- [2] eCPRI, <http://www.cpri.info/press.html>, March 2017.
- [3] 3GPP TSG RAN WG3, www.3gpp.org/ftp.
- [4] Ericsson Technology Review, "4G/5G RAN architecture: how a split can make the difference", July 2016.
- [5] F. Musumeci et al., OFC, M2G.4, Los Angeles, 2017.
- [6] M. R. Raza, et al., JOCN, vol. 8, no. 8, 2016.
- [7] 3GPP TSG RAN WG3, R3-161785, August, 2016.